

AI-Enhanced Velocity Prediction for Efficient EV Energy Management with Hybrid Storage

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Abstract—This research introduces an innovative approach to improve energy management in electric fleet vehicles by employing Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS) based on user driving velocity profiles. The study utilizes a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network to predict velocity profiles using historical data. The LSTM-derived velocity predictions serve as inputs for the Energy Management System (EMS) of the HESS, enabling anticipation of the vehicle’s power demand. This accurate anticipation allows the EMS to optimize energy flow within the system, resulting in improved energy efficiency, reduced range anxiety, smoother driving experiences, extended battery life, and enhanced energy recovery from braking. The developed LSTM neural network demonstrates the ability to predict the velocity of 21 drive cycles with good accuracy, exhibiting a maximum Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 1.94. This prediction capability is crucial for anticipating the energy demand of the vehicle. The research lays the foundation for a user-centric solution with significant potential to enhance energy management in electric fleet vehicles employing hybrid energy storage systems.

Index Terms—HESS, EMS, LSTM, velocity prediction, energy prediction, fleet management, user driving pattern.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric Vehicles (EVs) face challenges such as extended charging times and limited range, amplified by energy-intensive electronic systems for features like autonomous driving and collision avoidance. These factors impact the vehicle’s range, weight, and volume due to added batteries [1]. To address these challenges, an intelligent Energy Management System (EMS) is essential which is part of the HELIOS project—an innovative initiative dedicated to developing a Hybrid Energy Storage System (HESS). This paper aids the EMS in anticipating power demand for balancing energy supply within the HESS with the vehicle’s consumption, thereby extending battery life and driving range. Balancing involves deactivating non-critical energy-consuming features when unnecessary and harvesting energy through braking [2]. Real-time energy management faces challenges from computational complexity and time delays. However, anticipating power requirements can mitigate these issues by allowing the shutdown of non-essential systems and preparing the HESS to deliver necessary energy [3]. This anticipatory approach can eliminate the response time during acceleration and braking, ensuring a smooth user driving experience in certain situations.

Fig. 1: Proposed system architecture of user-specific energy management of electric fleet vehicles.

Accurate power consumption predictions enables the EMS to proactively adjust charging and driving strategies, resulting in improved range extension, reduced range anxiety, and maximized energy recapture through regenerative braking. Utilizing user driving patterns for energy consumption prediction is a key strategy [4]. There are several literature related to the optimization of the energy consumption of the EV [5]. Genetic Algorithm and Particle Swarm Optimization are used to for EMS based on fuzzy control strategy in MATLAB/Advisor [6]. Model predictive control has been used to manage power in the EV [7]. Another research deals in using Vehicle-to-Cloud technique to develop an efficient EMS consisting of HESS of battery and supercapacitor for electrical bus based on driving pattern recognition [8]. It is possible to improve the energy economy by predicting the driving cycle using the energy consumption characteristics of the driving condition of the hybrid electric buses [9]. Many fleet management services offer free-floating parking, granting riders parking flexibility [10]. In this context, real-time prediction of energy consumption becomes crucial due to unpredictable rider trajectories. Storing historical driving profiles for all users and generating individual prediction models in the vehicle isn’t feasible.

Therefore, it is proposed to use a combined cloud-edge system for efficient energy management as shown in Fig.1.

Section II describes the proposed energy management system comprising of the user driving pattern prediction and the vehicle energy consumption prediction for the energy management of the HESS. Section III presents the datasets and the parameters used for training the LSTM model. Section IV presents the results obtained and finally Section V summarizes the conclusions of this paper.

II. ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The user-specific driving pattern prediction model is generated based on the historical data of the users stored in the cloud database and then sent to the EV on demand. This user-specific driving pattern prediction model is used for predicting the velocity of the EV in real-time on the edge. The velocity forecast is then used for predicting the energy consumption of the EV in real-time which is then passed on to the EMS of HESS of the EV. The EMS of the HESS will split or balance the power between High Energy (HE) cells and High Power (HP) cells of the HESS enabling maximum energy recapture by the high power cells during braking, extending battery lifetime, smoother driving experience because of improved acceleration, etc.

Fig. 2: Flowchart of energy management process at system level

The flowchart of the energy management process at system level is shown in Fig. 2. At the start of the ride, the vehicle sends information to the cloud about the user who is going to ride the vehicle. Depending on the user, the cloud sends the user specific prediction model to the vehicle for energy consumption prediction. The user driving pattern prediction model along with real-time velocity, vehicle information, and ambient information is used to predict the energy consumption

of the vehicle. Later, the EMS manages the energy flow in the HESS. If the prediction error is greater than the predefined threshold then entire ride information acquired by the vehicle is sent to the cloud for remodelling the user driving pattern prediction model for the future ride.

A. Cloud-based: User Driving Pattern Prediction Model

Tailoring EVs to individual users can minimize energy consumption, but commercial EVs cater to general users due to the impracticality of making user-specific models. Therefore, the feasible way to optimize the energy consumption of the EV is by training the EMS of the EV for a specific user. Designing and developing an EV is complex and time-consuming. Simulations using software like MATLAB/Simulink are practical and commonly employed [11]. An example prototype confirmed the accuracy of computer-aided power consumption models for EVs [12], demonstrating their value for estimation of power consumption. Diverse driving patterns result from various real-time events during rides, such as traffic signals, congestion, road conditions, and more. The driving pattern is directly reflected in the velocity-time graph Fig.3. Therefore, forecasting the emergence of upward and downward velocity trends equates to predicting a user's driving pattern.

Fig. 3: Velocity versus Time graph of Artemis Urban Drive Cycle

Moreover, precisely determining vehicle velocity is challenging, forecasting peak and valley trends in the driving profile suffices for estimating energy consumption. Velocity versus time is a time series graph as seen in Fig.3. Therefore, prediction of the velocity can be done using different techniques like nonlinear Auto Regressive Moving Average (ARMA), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), etc. among others. The long term prediction of vehicle velocity is not feasible however the short term prediction is possible. Research suggests that in general the deterministic methods perform better and more specifically the LSTM gives the best results [13]. The vehicle velocity prediction using LSTM was exploited for the implementation of optimal EMS in the 2017 Toyota Prius Prime using Dynamic Programming (DP) [14]. Another study demonstrated that LSTM performs better than RNN in predicting vehicle velocity [15]. Therefore, in the proposed work, LSTM-NN is selected for the prediction of the velocity as it gives high accuracy for time series prediction [16].

Fig. 4: The basic structure of the LSTM Neural Network

1) *Long Short Term Neural Network*: LSTM NN is a special type of Recurrent Neural Network with the architecture that allows the network to only save the relevant information and forget the irrelevant information during the training process. LSTM cells are made of memory blocks capable of storing, reading, writing and forgetting information using logic gates that are closed or opened depending on the weights as shown in Fig.4 where $X(t)$ is the current input vector to the cell, $C(t)$ is the current memory state of the cell, $H(t)$ represents the current cell output value and σ is the sigmoid function which controls the flow of information into and out of the cell state. All the input samples of X are passed through the LSTM cells. In general, the outputs $C(t)$ and $H(t)$ of each cell depends on the past inputs $X(t-1)$ and outputs $C(t-1)$ and $H(t-1)$. Each LSTM cell has 4 gates. They are the forget gate, input modulation gate, input gate and output gate. i.e. $F(t)$, $G(t)$, $I(t)$ and $O(t)$ respectively. The input modulation gate uses tanh function to control the update of the cell state, and also as a part of the output calculation whereas the input gate, output gate and forget gate is controlled by the sigmoid function which outputs a value between 0 and 1 based on the value of $H(t-1)$. The output values from the 4 gates are further processed with the help of basic mathematical operators to compute the final outputs of the LSTM cell.

Using the below-mentioned equations the output values $C(t)$ and $H(t)$ of LSTM cells are calculated

$$F(t) = \sigma(W_f X(t) + R_f H(t-1) + b_f) \quad (1)$$

$$I(t) = \sigma(W_i X(t) + R_i H(t-1) + b_i) \quad (2)$$

$$G(t) = \tanh(W_g X(t) + R_g H(t-1) + b_g) \quad (3)$$

$$O(t) = \sigma(W_o X(t) + R_o H(t-1) + b_o) \quad (4)$$

$$C(t) = F(t) \cdot C(t-1) + I(t) \cdot G(t) \quad (5)$$

$$H(t) = O(t) \cdot \tanh(C(t)) \quad (6)$$

where W is the weight, R is the recurrent weight and b is the bias value of the respective gate.

Depending on the application, the neural network consists of different numbers of layers. However, the three basic

layers required to create a neural network are Input Layer, Hidden Layer and the Output Layer. The optional layers that can be added are Dropout Layer, Fully Connected Layer and additional Hidden Layers. Fig.4 demonstrates the basic structure of the LSTM neural network. The time series vector $X(t)$ is passed through the input layer. Each sample of the time series vector $X(t)$ is passed through all the neurons in the hidden layer. In this case, LSTM is the hidden layer so each neuron is an LSTM cell. The output of each LSTM cell is an input to the rest of the LSTM cells in the hidden layer. In Fully Connected Layer the outputs from all the LSTM cells are added and updated to output the predicted samples.

2) *Neural network training and Hyperparameter selection*: Neural networks should be trained for multiple epochs for improved accuracy. An epoch is a training iteration of 1 complete cycle where the entire training dataset goes through the entire neural network. During this process the weights of the neural network are adjusted. However, care must be taken in selecting the appropriate number of epochs as less epoch results in under-fitting and more epoch leads to overfitting. If the training dataset is huge and the entire training dataset is passed through the neural network in one forward pass then it leads to insufficient memory related issues. In order to avoid such issues the entire training dataset can be split into small chunks or batches. Depending on the batch size all the batches of the training dataset are passed individually through the network and the network is optimized through back propagation for every iteration. For example, a dataset of 1000 images and a batch size of 10 will have to undergo 100 iterations to complete 1 epoch.

Fig. 5: Proposed algorithm to train LSTM network

Selecting the right hyperparameters for the machine learning model yields the highest possible accuracy. However, the machine learning models cannot determine its best combination of hyperparameters. Therefore, it is necessary to try different configurations of hyperparameter values during the training process to achieve the highest accuracy. The different parameters like solver type, learning rate, LSTM layers, neurons in each LSTM layer, batch size and L2 regularization

can be varied between a certain range to determine the best combination of hyperparameters. As shown in Fig. 5, the first step is to create an LSTM NN and train the network with the training and validation data. Later, select the parameters that might optimize the proposed machine learning model. After selecting these parameters, a maximum and minimum range is selected for each parameter. Correspondingly, different models are created according to the different ranges of each parameter. All the models will output Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) which is the most common parameter for evaluating the performance of an LSTM NN model. The model with the least RMSE is selected to train the network with an increased number of iterations as compared to the one used during hyperparameter selection. Finally, the resulting neural network model is tested using the test data.

B. Edge-based: Energy Consumption Prediction for EMS of HESS

Urban environments feature frequent braking and acceleration due to traffic signals. Harnessing kinetic energy from braking to aid acceleration enhances efficiency. Both actions generate momentary peaks ideally stored and utilized within high-power-density batteries. Various studies explore maximizing energy harvesting via regenerative braking [17]. Properly sizing ultracapacitors and power electronics minimizes ESS mass [18]. Efficient HESS utilization involves control strategy [19]. Several studies demonstrate different techniques to maximize energy harvesting in electric vehicles using regenerative braking [17]. Understanding the relationship between sizing the ultracapacitor and the sizing of the power electronics is imperative to minimize the mass of ESS in EV [18]. Other than the sizing of HESS, the control strategy for the system performance and efficient utilization of HESS is also an important factor [19]. Therefore, in this project, the speed prediction can be exploited to maximize the advantages of both the high energy cell and the high power cell of the Hybrid Energy Storage System (HESS).

The energy consumption of the vehicle can be calculated using the following equations [20]:

$$E = \int_0^T P(t) dt \quad (7)$$

where, E [Joules] – Energy consumption of the vehicle, P [Watt] – Power of the battery pack, T [sec] – Time period the energy of the battery is being consumed.

$$P = F_{\text{tot}} \cdot V \quad (8)$$

where, F_{tot} [N] – the total force, V [m/s] – the velocity of the vehicle.

$$F_{\text{tot}} = F_t + F_r + F_s + F_a \quad (9)$$

$$F_t = M \cdot a \quad (10)$$

where, F_t [N] – the acceleration force, M [kg] – total mass of the vehicle, a [m/s²] – acceleration of the vehicle.

$$M = kw \cdot mf + dw \cdot n \quad (11)$$

where, kw [kg] – Vehicle kerb weight, mf [-] – Vehicle mass factor, dw [kg] – Driver weight, n [-] – Number of people.

$$F_r = M \cdot g \cdot Cr \cdot \cos(\alpha) \quad (12)$$

where, F_r [N] – the rolling force, Cr [-] – tire friction coefficient, g [m/s²] – gravitational acceleration, α [rad] – road slope angle.

$$F_s = M \cdot g \cdot \sin(\alpha) \quad (13)$$

where, F_s [N] – the grading slope force.

$$F_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho \cdot Cd \cdot A \cdot v^2 \quad (14)$$

where, F_a [N] – the aerodynamic force, ρ [kg/m³] – air density at 20°C, Cd [-] – air drag coefficient, A [m²] – vehicle frontal area, v [m/s] – velocity of the vehicle.

Therefore, by substituting equations (10) to (14) in equation (9), the total force experienced by the vehicle can be calculated, and by substituting equation (9) in equation (8), the power needed by the vehicle can be known, and thereby the energy consumption of the vehicle by substituting equation (8) in equation (7). As seen from the above equations, the energy consumption of the vehicle depends mostly on the velocity of the vehicle. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the present paper exclusively focuses on velocity prediction. The anticipation of energy consumption, however, will be incorporated in the extended phase of this research.

III. DATASET

A. Driving Cycle Dataset

Fig. 6: Image of the trajectory used for experimental data

There exists a dataset of the vehicle energy consumption however the vehicles used are mainly ICE, PHEV and HEV [21]. User-specific historical data of velocity versus time is not easily accessible. Therefore, to check the feasibility of the driving pattern prediction model, the dataset used comprises 13 standard driving cycles as listed in Table I as training data along with 1 driving cycle acquired experimentally as validation data. The experimental data is estimated from the GPS data of the test vehicle. Fig.6 shows the google maps image of the trajectory of the test ride. The total drive time of the 14 driving cycles amounts to 13032 seconds whereas the maximum velocity is 35.90 km/hr and the average velocity is 9.98 km/hr.

TABLE I: Training Drive Cycle Dataset

Drive Cycle	Time (Sec)	Max (m/s)	Average (m/s)
FTP75	2474	25.35	7.18
FTP72	1372	25.35	8.73
US06	600	35.90	21.44
SC03	600	24.50	9.59
HWFET	765	26.78	21.55
NYCC	598	12.38	3.17
HUDDS	1060	25.93	8.42
LA92	1435	30.04	11.00
LA92 Short	969	30.04	11.60
IM240	240	25.35	13.08
UDDS	1369	25.35	8.75
ECE Extra UDC	400	25.00	16.48
Artemis Urban	993	16.03	4.90
Test Vehicle Data	157	24.27	4.49
Total	13032	35.90	9.98

B. Software tools and Hardware Specifications

Deep Network Designer application from MATLAB was used to create the LSTM neural network and the Experiment Manager application was used to sweep through a range of hyperparameter values. The deep learning model and Simulink simulations were performed on a laptop with x64-based processor Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-1035G1 CPU @ 1.00GHz and 8 GB RAM.

IV. RESULTS

A. LSTM based Velocity Prediction

An univariate LSTM model where the input and the output are one-dimensional is developed. The dataset is a one dimensional array of velocity versus time with a sampling rate of 1 per second. The speed and velocity are same in this work as the user direction considered is longitudinal and unidirectional. The dataset consisting of 13032 seconds is split into 90% for training and 10% for validation. To reduce the computational complexity, the dataset is downscaled between 0 and 1 using the standardization method. The LSTM cells in each layer are the neurons in the layer. More neurons give the model high dimensionality that are useful to capture the peaks and valleys. Using a dropout layer will randomly ignore some percentage of neurons during each iteration of training.

The LSTM network created consisted of 5 layers i.e. input layer, 1 LSTM layer, dropout layer, fully connected layer and output regression layer. 200 LSTM neurons were added in the LSTM layer. Training dataset was iterated for 250 epochs. For optimizing the training, Adam solver was used with an initial learning rate of 0.005 with a drop in the learning rate by a factor of 0.2 after 125 epochs. It took 25 min and 54 seconds for training the network on a single CPU hardware configuration. The specification of developed LSTM NN model is listed in Table II. 'C' refers to the cell state that stores the information that the network has accumulated so far, 'B' refers to the batch size that are processed together simultaneously and 'T' refers to the time steps or sequence length. The created model was then used to predict the validation data. The model is designed in order to predict the velocity 1 second in advance. Finally, the validation data is compared with the predicted output from

TABLE II: Specifications of the developed LSTM NN model

Layers	Activations	Learnable Properties	No. of Learnables	States
Sequence Input	1 x 1 x 1 C x B x T	-	0	-
LSTM	200 x 1 x 1	InputWeights: 800 x 1 RecurrentWeights: 800 x 200 Bias 800 x 1	161600	Hidden State: 200 x 1 Cell State: 200 x 1
Dropout	200 x 1 x 1	-	0	-
Fully Connected	1 x 1 x 1	Weights: 1 x 200 Bias: 1 x 1	201	-
Regression	1 x 1 x 1	-	0	-

Fig. 7: Forecasting the velocity or speed of the vehicle using the created LSTM NN.

Fig. 8: Regression line of the test data versus the predicted data.

the LSTM NN model and it results in an Regression line R or slope of 0.99 and an RMSE of 1.1 as shown on Fig.8 and Fig.7.

The LSTM network was trained on the dataset (Table I) and applied to predict velocities in Simulink using various drive cycles. A model with Drive Cycle Source and Stateful Predict blocks was created. The Drive Cycle Source block provides input datasets to the Stateful Predict block, containing the

TABLE III: Results of velocity prediction of the various drive cycles using the created LSTM NN

Drive Cycle	Time (Sec)	RMSE
WLTP Class 1	1022	0.28
WLTP Class 2	1477	0.36
WLTP Class 3	1800	0.62
ECE R15 Single Cycle	195	0.37
ECE R15 Four Cycles	780	0.37
EUDC	400	0.43
NEDC	1180	0.40
ADAC BAB 130	795	1.94
Artemis Rural Road	1082	0.56
Artemis Motorway 130 kmph	1068	1.097
JC08	1204	0.40
WHVC	900	0.39
Braunschweig City Driving Cycle	1740	0.55
Central Business District	560	0.58
CUEDC diesel cycle - MC	1723	0.66
ETC FIGE Version 4	1800	0.37
RTS 95	886	0.94
CUEDC SPC240	240	0.60
CUEDC petrol cycle	499	0.46
BAC - Commuter Cycle	310	0.46
Orange County Bus Cycle	1909	0.50

LSTM NN. Accuracy was evaluated using RMSE calculated across 21 separate drive cycles (Table III), demonstrating the LSTM's effective velocity prediction capabilities. The maximum RMSE of 1.94 corresponds to ADAC BAB 130 drive cycle and the minimum RMSE of 0.28 corresponds to the WLTP Class 1 drive cycle.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In order to optimize energy management for electric vehicles, this study focuses on predicting user driving velocity to estimate power demand. The developed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network exhibits robust predictive capabilities across 21 diverse drive cycles, achieving a maximum Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 1.94 in velocity predictions. Notably, the model excels in accuracy, with an impressive RMSE of 0.28 when tested against the challenging WLTP Class 1 drive cycle. This research highlights the pivotal role of energy management, emphasizing the integration of our predictive model with Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS). The innovative fusion of precise predictive insights and advanced energy storage solutions creates new pathways for sustainable transportation.

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